

MONOCLONAL ANTIBODIES: AN EMERGING IMMUNOTHERAPY TECHNOLOGY

Shafras Mahroof^{1*}, Geetika Pant¹ and Rukshan Rafeek²

¹Department of Biotechnology Indian Academy Degree College, Bangalore-43, India.

²Department of Microbiology Faculty of Medicine University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.

*Author for Correspondence: Shafras Mahroof

Department of Biotechnology Indian Academy Degree College, Bangalore-43, India.

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ABSTRACT

Antibodies of a single idotype produced by immortalized B cells are called monoclonal antibodies which are mono-specific in nature. Its specificity serves as a detector for purify almost any given substance. The Y shaped structure of antibodies consist of 2 heavy chains and 2 light chains with one variable region which gives antibody its specificity for binding antigen and 3 constant regions determines the mechanism used to destroy antigen. The development of hybridization techniques allowed for production of one kind of specific antibody by immortalized antibody-producing cells. Methods were then developed to screen for and produce large numbers of these antibodies for use in many applications, mAbs in biomedical research play a role in identification of proteins, carbohydrates and nucleic acids. Their use has led to the elucidation of many molecules that control cell replication and differentiation. This technology has improved the understanding of the host response to infectious –disease agents and toxins produced by these agents, to transplanted organs and tissues, to spontaneously transformed cells and to endogenous antigens. The exquisite specificity of mAb allows them to used in humans and animals for disease diagnosis and treatment.

KEY WORDS: Monoclonal Antibody, Hybridoma Technology, Applications, Types, Side effects.

INTRODUCTION

The vertebrate immune system is rapidly evolving to protect itself from different intruding pathogens. The vertebrate immune system response for the foreign pathogen by producing complementary antibody (Ab) molecules that can bind to all molecular structures of the microbial pathogen (bacteria, viruses, fungi, nematodes, and other parasites) and can keep pace with the diversified mutations in an organism. Any particle that enters the body can be recognized by vertebrate immune system as a foreign entity is defined as antigen. Thus the immune system is combated in two ways. First, by, B lymphocytes produce varied antibodies specific for a new antigen (epitope). Second, paratope-encoding genes of the antibody are mutated rapidly to cope and bind strongly with the epitope of the antigen. Thus, these produced antibodies are better at binding with the antigen with strong affinity and high specificity.^[1]

Antibodies developed in the blood of immunized animals from different cell types are called as Polyclonal antibodies and are not mono-specific.^[2] As most antigens bear multiple epitopes, they can stimulate the proliferation and differentiation of a variety of B-cell clones in to polyclonal antibodies.^[3] Antibodies Produced by homogeneous hybrid cells (B cells) are Monoclonal antibodies (mAb or moAb) and are mono specific.^[4, 5] Due to the specificity of MAb they can be

serve as detector for purify almost any given substance.^[6] Their specificity and high reproducibility of MAbs serve advantage over polyclonal antibodies. This has become an important tool in biochemistry, molecular biology and medicine. Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) are currently used for many diagnostic and therapeutic applications. The high demand for these biopharmaceuticals has led to the development of large-scale manufacturing processes, with productivity improvements and optimization of bioreactor systems.^[7]

Antibody Structure

An antibody is a “Y” shaped glycoprotein, which contains two light chains and two heavy chains, which are linked by multiple disulphide bonds called Hinge region. This helps in the antibody rotation. Heavy chain is made up of one variable region (V_H) & 3 constant regions (C_H) except for IgM & IgE. IgM & IgE having an extra C_H domain. Light chain is having one variable region & one constant region. Variable region is called as variable since it's varies according to the epitope. Variable region, also known as the Fab (fragment antigen binding) region, and a constant region, which is also known as the Fc (fragment crystalizable) region. The antigen binding complementarity determining regions (CDRs) are short hyper variable amino acid sequences found in the variable domains of both light and heavy chains. Each of the two chains contains three CDRs

(CDR1, CDR2 and CDR3). CDRs are synonymous with hyper variable domains because the majority of the sequence variations associated with antibodies are found in the CDRs. Among the six CDRs in an IgG molecule, CDR3s have the greatest variability. After binding to a target, a mAb can recruit effector cells such as natural killer cells, macrophages or neutrophils or activate complement to destroy the target-associated cells. These actions are referred to as antibody-dependent cell

cytotoxicity (ADCC) and complement-dependent cytotoxicity (CDC). Both ADCC and CDC are resulted from the combined functions of Fab and Fc portions of the mAb. The Fc region is the tail region of an antibody. In IgG, IgA and IgD antibody isotypes, the Fc region is composed of two identical protein fragments, derived from the second and third constant domains of the antibody's two heavy chains. The IgG isotype is most commonly used in therapeutic applications.^[8]

Figure 1: Antibodies are immune system related proteins called immunoglobulins. Each antibody consists of four polypeptides –two heavy chains and two light chains joint to form a “Y” shaped molecule. The amino acid sequence in the tips of the “Y” varies greatly among different antibodies. This variable region gives the antibody its specificity for binding antigen. The constant region determines the mechanism used to destroy antigen.

Source

https://www.google.lk/search?q=antibody+structure&espv=2&biw=1366&bih=667&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwji8e6MgK_KAhVD0xoKHR8TBuQQ_AUIB#imgrc=dDR_JhMh823qXM%3A

Different types of synthetic Monoclonal Antibodies

Murine Antibodies

Antibody-secreting spleen cells from immunized mice fused with a murine myeloma cell line to generate immortalized cell lines that secreted individual, or monoclonal, antibodies. This was the first MAb developed for use as potential human therapeutics. While initial interest in these murine MAbs was high, OKT3 was the only murine monoclonal antibody that was approved for human therapeutic use. Despite the fact that OKT3 has been moderately successful in the market, the use of murine MAbs as therapeutic agents quickly ran into many roadblocks. One of the potential advantages of MAbs as therapeutic agents is their long circulating half-

life, allowing them to provide a therapeutic effect in patients over several days. However, when murine MAbs were repeatedly administered to humans during clinical trials, it was observed that the half-life decreased and the products became less effective with each injection. This was because of the immunogenicity of murine proteins in humans and the rapid development of a human anti murine antibody (HAMA) response in the patients. This HAMA response neutralized the effectiveness of the murine antibodies and resulted in their rapid clearance from the body. For example, it has been reported that OKT3 can elicit a HAMA response in up to 86% of patients treated, leading to some limitations in its efficacy.^[9]

Figure2: Different types of monoclonal antibody.

Source:

http://www.nature.com/nrc/journal/v6/n9/fig_tab/nrc1913_F1.html

Chimeric Antibodies

Several approaches were developed to overcome this HAMA response, for making MABs more human-like and less immunogenic. In the early 1990s, “chimeric” antibodies were developed by linking the murine genes encoding the antigen binding portion of the antibody (the variable region) to the genes encoding the constant region of human immunoglobulin light and heavy chains. More than 75% of the protein sequence of the resulting chimeric antibodies was of human origin; these chimeric MABs resulted in lower HAMA responses in patients. Chimeric antibody products are superior to murine antibody products however they still pose a moderate risk of immunogenicity to patients this made molecular biology researchers to generate fully “humanized” antibody products.

Humanized Antibodies

The antigen binding specificity of any antibody is determined by the amino acids present in three distinct highly variable regions per antibody chain, referred to as complementarity determining regions (CDRs), and located in a more conserved framework sequence in the variable regions. In 1991, Protein Design Labs (PDL) developed methods for engineering an antibody gene in which the CDRs of a human antibody gene were replaced by those from the CDR of a murine MAB gene. The resulting humanized antibody has the same antigen binding properties as the original murine antibody but contains minimal murine sequences and, therefore, elicits lower HAMA response in patients. Like chimeric antibodies, humanized antibodies can activate other parts of the immune system to create a more effective product. Several humanized antibody products are currently on the market, including Synagis (approved in 1998), Herceptin (approved in 1998), Mylotarg (approved

in 2000), Xolair (approved in 2003), and Avastin (approved in 2004). Further to minimize the HAMA response technologies like human engineering or deimmunization developed.^[10]

Fully Human Antibodies

Fully human sequence derived antibodies have no murine sequence, and are largely produced by two general technologies—*in vivo* approaches using a murine system in which the immunoglobulin genes have been replaced by their human counterparts or *in vitro* approaches using libraries containing millions of variations of antibody sequences coupled with a mechanism to express and screen these antibodies *in vitro*. The first fully human sequence-derived antibody to be approved for therapeutic use was adalimumab (Humira), a fully human IgG1 antibody specific for TNFalpha that was selected via phage display. In the market place, this human mAb competes with Enbrel, an Fc fusion protein, and Remicade, a chimeric antibody. The power of the fully human antibody platform can be seen in the sales figures for these three products shown in Table 1. Humira has successfully taken a significant market share from them, garnering almost 16% market share in 2006. There will be exceptions to this generalization, for example when a short half life is desired or when a toxic or radioactive payload is linked to the antibody.

Table 1: Comparison of sales for antibody-based anti-inflammatory

Product	Company	Year approved	2006 sales worldwide (\$ millions)	Market share
Humira	Abbott	2002	2,000	15.8%
Remicade	Johnson & Johnson	1998	4,253	33.7%
Enbrel	Amgen	1998	4,379	34.7%

Production of Hybridoma

Hybridoma technology is a popular technique use to produced Monoclonal antibodies in specialized cells. Hybridoma technology was discovered in 1975 by two scientists, Georges Kohler and Cesar Milstein, who jointly with Niels Jerne.^[1]

Hybridomas are hybrid cell lines that are generated through the fusion of an antibody-producing B cell with a myeloma (B cell cancer) cell that have been engineered to produce a desired antibody in large amounts, to produce monoclonal antibodies. Myeloma cells are characterized by the ability to grow in tissue cultures and the absence of antibody chain synthesis.^[2]

Figure 3: Selection of fused cells (Hybridoma) using HAT medium

Source

https://www.google.lk/search?q=images+for+HAT+selection&espv=2&biw=1366&bih=667&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=0CAYQ_AUoAWoVChMIn8vCx5eFyQIVzr-OCh1JOAYS#imgrc=7Qt6jTG5kT82AM%3A

Polyethylene glycol is used as fusing agent to fuse adjacent plasma membranes, but the success rate is

usually low so a selective medium in which only fused cells can grow is used. This is possible due to myeloma cells which have lost the ability to synthesize hypoxanthine-guanine-phosphoribosyltransferase (HGPRT), an enzyme necessary for the salvage synthesis of nucleic acids.^[6]

The selective culture medium is called HAT medium because it contains hypoxanthine, aminopterin, and thymidine. This medium is selective for fused (hybridoma) cells. Unfused myeloma cells cannot grow because they lack HGPRT, and thus cannot replicate their DNA. Unfused spleen cells cannot grow indefinitely because of their limited life span. Only fused hybrid cells, referred to as hybridomas, are able to grow indefinitely in this media because the spleen cell partner supplies HGPRT and the myeloma partner is characteristic that make it immortal (similar to a cancer cell). This mixture of cells is then diluted and clones are grown (from single parent cells) on microtiter wells. The antibodies secreted by the different clones are then assayed for their ability to bind to the antigen with ELISA or Antigen Microarray Assay or immuno-dot blot.

Production of murine monoclonal antibodies

Figure 4: Step wise description of Monoclonal Antibody Production

SOURCE

https://www.google.lk/search?q=monoclonal+antibody+production+sridhar+rao&espv=2&biw=1366&bih=623&site=webhp&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEWjSm9TWpqfKAhUDPhQKHQghDRoQ_AUIBigB#imgrc=n1XyNHTmhSedoM%3A

Procedure**Step 1: Immunization of Mice and Selection of Mouse Donors for Generation of Hybridoma Cells**

Mice are immunized with an antigen that is prepared for injection either by emulsifying the antigen with Freund's adjuvant or other adjuvants. In general, mice are immunized every 2-3 weeks.

Step 2: Screening of Mice for Antibody Production

After several weeks of immunization, blood samples are obtained from mice for measurement of serum antibodies. Serum antibody titer is determined with various techniques, such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). When the antibody titer is high enough, the mice are euthanized and their spleens removed for *in vitro* Hybridoma cell production.

Step 3: Fusion of Myeloma Cells with Immune Spleen Cells

Spleen cells from the immunized mouse are fused with the previously prepared myeloma cells. Fusion is accomplished by a technique called somatic cell hybridization. This is achieved by co-centrifuging freshly harvested spleen cells and myeloma cells in polyethylene glycol, a substance that causes cell membranes to fuse.

Step 4: Selection of Hybridoma cells

Those myeloma cells that have lost the ability to synthesize any antibody molecules of their own and lack enzyme hypoxanthine-guanine-phosphoribosyl transferase (HGPRT) are selected. They are both HGPRT⁻ and Ig⁻. This enzyme enables cells to synthesize purines using an extracellular source of hypoxanthine as a precursor. Ordinarily, the absence of HGPRT is not a problem for the cell because cells have an alternate pathway that they can use to synthesize purines. However, when cells are exposed to aminopterin, they are unable to use this other pathway and are now fully dependent on HGPRT for survival. The mouse derived B cells have this enzyme and can produce antibodies too. They are HGPRT⁺ and Ig⁺. The cells are then placed in HAT (hypoxanthine, aminopterin, thymidine) medium. Since the unfused myeloma cells lack HGPRT and aminopterin disallows alternative pathway, they die. Unfused B Cells are mortal and cannot proliferate, so they too die. Only the hybridoma cells that have the ability to multiply immortally and possess HGPRT will survive. The HAT medium allows only the fused cells to survive in culture.

Step 5: Checking for Hybridoma cells

The supernatants from each culture are tested to find those producing the desired antibody. Since there may be

more than one hybridoma cell in the original cultures, single cells from each antibody-positive culture must be isolated and subcultured. The supernatant of each must be tested for the desired antibodies.

Step 6: Cloning of Hybridoma Cell Lines

There are two methods for growing these cells: injecting them into the peritoneal cavity of a mouse or using *in vitro* cell-culture techniques. When injected into a mouse, the hybridoma cells multiply and produce fluid (ascites) in its abdomen; this fluid contains a high concentration of antibody. The other alternative is to grow hybridoma cells in *in vitro* culture medium. Further processing of the mouse ascitic fluid and of the tissue-culture supernatant might be required to obtain mAb with the required purity and concentration.

Factors affecting Murine Monoclonal Antibody Production

1. Age

- A fully immunocompetent mouse is acquired at about 4yrs of age.

2. Nutritional Status:

- Mice should be physically stable, without disease, malnutrition.

3. Dose of Antigen

- An Ag is immunogenic only when administered above a minimal critical dose- neither very small dose nor very large dose.

4. Route of Administration

- Parental administration of Ag shows better humoral response than oral or nasal routes.
- Oral or nasal routes suitable for Ig A production.
- Inhalation of pollen Ag by nasal routes induces IgE production.

5. Adjuvants

- Substances when injected together with Ag that enhance Ab production are called adjuvant.
- It enhances slow release of soluble Ag prolonging antigenic stimulus.

6. Immunosuppressive Agents

- Agents such as X-irradiation, alkylating agents, corticosteroids inhibit immune response in mice
- It can cause complete suppression of Ab response.

Human Monoclonal Antibodies

To avoid some of the side effects of humanised and Chimeric antibodies the scientists have targeted to create 'fully' human antibodies. Two methods were identified namely Phage display-generated antibodies and Mice genetically engineered to produce human-like antibodies.

Guidelines to cell engineering for Monoclonal Antibody production

Currently there are number of approved monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) used in clinical trials and therapeutic purposes.^[13] mAbs production in mammalian cells consists of a long process which involves steps of transfection of the desired genes into the target cells, clone selection, adaptation to different culture conditions (usually suspension and serum-free medium), culture in

bioreactors and scale-up to industrial level.^[14] For this, the optimization of mAb production is usually performed in bioreactors, by testing different bioreactor, their modes of operation and culture parameters. In fact, it is known that several parameters such as cell line type, cell size and cell cycle, product characteristics, vector/promoter of transfection, methods of clone selection, post-transcription regulation and growth medium, among many others, have great impact on the final productivity levels obtained.^[15]

Expression system

At present for commercial production of mAbs mammalian cells are the main hosts. The reason behind the use of mammalian cells are, they have the ability to perform correct (human-like), post-translational modifications.^[16] Production of mAbs in these cells necessarily begins with the development of a suitable cell line, determined by the selection of cell type. In order to be applied for biopharmaceutical application, cells must have the following characteristics.

- (i) support high-level product expression over long periods of time maintaining high viable cell density and genetic stability,
- (ii) Be scalable,
- (iii) Have appropriate abilities for post-translational processing and
- (iv) Allow appropriate characterization for human safety.^[17]

Moreover, depend on the product application the choice of the best suitable cell line may varies. The African green monkey kidney (COS) cells are appropriate to produce small-scale quantities of mAbs. For the large-scale production, the most currently used cells are Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells, which have proved their importance both in laboratory and biopharmaceutical high-level mAb production.^[16] Their suitability for large-scale and stable production of mAbs is due to their advantages of safety for use in humans, resemblance between glycan structure of their product with the natural human mAb, ease of transfection, presence of a powerful gene amplification system, ease of adaptation to growth in suspension and serum-free medium, and the ability to grow at high densities. Other cells commonly used for large-scale production are myeloma cells.^[13,18]

A variety of cell lines can be used for mAb production, although not all have the ability to achieve high-level of expression. However, the levels of expression appear to be more dependent on the combination of host cell, expression vector, transfection and selection strategy, rather than on only the characteristics of the host cell.^[17]

Transfection

Selected most suitable cell type (for the application intended), cells are transfected to obtain mAb-producing clones. Transfection is the introduction of the product DNA into the cells by non-viral methods, and it involves

several steps for the selection of the transfected cells with the most desirable characteristics.^[17, 19]

Expression vector

Specialized vectors are used to transfer the product gene into the cells to express heterologous proteins in mammalian cells.^[20]

In certain cases foreign gene fails to express in a host cell due to the following reasons

1. They may not have a strong promoter to control the expression of the gene
2. Sometimes promoter result in the expression but transcription fails
3. Terminator sequence may not be available to stop the protein synthesis or initiation codon

Therefore certain vectors constructed with proper expression signal transcribe and translate the foreign gene in a host cell such a vector is called as expression vector.

Due to these requirements, mammalian vectors are usually plasmids.^[20] For the expression of recombinant proteins in mammalian cells, a strong viral promoter/enhancer or a cellular promoter/enhancer combination known to be particularly active to a certain host cell are mostly used.^[17] When the mammalian expression vectors are used for generation of a stable producing cell line, an extra sequence, encoding a selectable marker gene, is used. This selection gene can be present on the same vector as the recombinant gene or in separate vectors, and can be driven from a weak promoter, in order to increase the possibility to obtain high level of producer cells.^[21] Furthermore, to improve the efficiency of stable transfection, plasmids can be linearized using restriction enzymes.^[20] Depending on the surrounding chromatin at the integration site, expression of the product can be high, low or even null.

The development of synthetic promoters could solve many problems but their application would probably be cell-line specific.^[22] Although a single vector system has the advantage of assuring equal introduction of genes into cells, the randomness of their integration into the cell genome remains a problem that results in inaccurate control of the relative expression of these genes.^[23]

Transfection methods

Diversity of methods and systems are available for the introduction of the desired product gene into the host mammalian cells in a transient or stable way.^[21] In transient transfection DNA is maintained/ replicated as an extra chromosomal unit, the expression ability is rapidly lost, only allowing the production of small (milligram to gram) quantities of mAbs.^[17, 22] Therefore, transient expression systems are not suitable for large-scale production.

DNA delivery systems

Several DNA delivery systems have been developed for the introduction of the genes of interest into mammalian

cells, among that non-viral gene transfer approaches being the most suitable for manufacturing purposes.^[21] These methods include calcium–phosphate precipitation, electroporation and lipofection & Polyfection.^[21, 22]

Calcium–phosphate precipitation

Calcium phosphate is an effective method for the production of long-term stable transfectants it is based on the formation of a fine DNA precipitate or complex that enters mammalian cells via an endocytic vesicle and has the advantages of being inexpensive and working in a wide range of cell type.^[17, 24] Nevertheless, the still low efficiencies of this method, the requirement of serum in the medium during transfection^[25], as well as the high variability of the transfection outcome depending on minor alterations in procedure (relative concentrations of reagents and DNA) or environment (pH, temperature)^[17], has led researchers to find better gene transfer methods.^[25]

Electroporation

In this method electrical pulse is used to introduce DNA into the cell by exposure to brief electric shock, the cell become temporarily permeable to DNA of the required DNA. This is a simple and rapid method used for genes delivery into cells. There are two systems of electroporation.

1. Low voltage- long pulses method
2. High voltage-short pulses method

Generally, low voltage-long pulses produce high rates of transient transformation, while high voltage short pulses give high rates of stable transformation. This method usually results in lower post-transfection cell viability. Consequently, this method is more commonly used in small assays that require rapid and low levels of production.^[17]

Lipofection and Polyfection

Lipofection and polyfection both are the most recent, and probably most simple, transfection methodologies for gene delivery in a diversity of cells. Lipofection consists of cationic lipid-mediated gene transfer into the cell, where cationic liposomes form a complex with the negatively charged DNA. This method can be performed in the presence or absence of serum, with little or no toxicity, as well as with attached and suspended cells.

Polyfection, for its turn, refers to the gene transfer mediated by cationic polymers such as polycationpolyethylenimine, PEI^[26] and dendrimers. They interact with DNA forming a polyplex that protects DNA from degradation before reaching the cell nucleus. This method can be used for gene delivery in serum-free suspension cultures.^[26]

Selection

After transfection, mAb-producing cells are selected by being subjected to specific culture conditions that only

allow survival and growth of cell clones expressing the marker gene products.^[17] These clones are transferred as single cells to a second cultivation vessel, where the cultures are expanded to produce clonal populations. Clones are then evaluated in terms of growth and product (mAb) titer, and the highest producers are selected for another round of cultivation and analysis, to confirm whether the levels of productivity are maintained.^[21] The gene of interest expressing the antibody may be co-amplified with the selective marker genes, resulting in enhanced expression levels and mAb productivity.^[17] However, other specific cell properties are also be important for the production process and should be included in the screening, such as.

- the ability of a clone to grow in serum free medium,
- resistance to apoptosis,
- cell characteristics (i.e. cell size has been considered the major cellular determinant of productivity,
- production kinetics suitable for the type of process used,
- stability of product formation and
- A general robustness of the cell line under the stress and shear conditions found in bioreactors.^[27]

Purification of Monoclonal Antibodies

After obtaining either a sample of cultured hybridoma cells or a sample of ascites fluid, the desired antibodies must be extracted. The contaminants in the cell culture sample may consist of impurities primarily media components such as growth factors, hormones, and transferrins. In contrast, the *in vivo* sample is prone to have host antibodies, proteases, nucleases, nucleic acids, and viruses. The sample is firstly conditioned, or prepared for purification. Cells, cell debris, lipids, and clotted material are first removed, typically by centrifugation followed by filtration with a 0.45 µm filter. These large particles can cause a phenomenon called membrane fouling in later purification steps. In addition, the concentration of product in the sample may not be sufficient, especially in cases where the desired antibodies are produced by a low-secreting cell line. The sample is therefore condensed by ultrafiltration or dialysis. Most of the charged impurities are usually anions such as nucleic acids and endotoxins. These are often separated by ion exchange chromatography.^[28] Either cation exchange chromatography is used at a low enough pH that the desired antibody binds to the column while anions flow through, or anion exchange chromatography is used at a high enough pH that the desired antibody flows through the column while anions bind to it.^[29]

The antibodies-containing media is then incubated with the immobilized antigens, either in batch or as the antibodies are passed through a column, where they selectively bind and can be retained while impurities are washed away. An elution with a low pH buffer or a gentler, high salt elution buffer is then used to recover purified antibodies from the support. To further select antibodies, the antibodies can be precipitated out using

sodium sulphate or ammonium sulphate. The final purity can be analyzed using a chromatogram. Any impurities will produce peaks, and the volume under the peak indicates the amount of the impurity in the sample. Alternatively, gel electrophoresis and capillary electrophoresis can be carried out. Impurities will produce bands of varying intensity; depending on how much of the impurity is present.^[28]

Long-term maintenance and cryo preservation of MABS

The selected hybridomas are cryo-preserved in liquid nitrogen in ampules which can be thawed for use in future studies. For long-term maintenance, it is always desirable to evaluate the quality of the produced antibody regularly because there may be some deterioration.^[3]

Applications of Monoclonal Antibodies

MABs have proved to be extremely valuable for basic immunological and molecular research because of their high specificity. They are used in human therapy, commercial protein purification, suppressing immune response, diagnosis of diseases, cancer therapy, diagnosis of allergy, hormone test, purification of complex mixtures, structure of cell membrane, identification of specialized cells, preparation of vaccines, and increasing the effectiveness of medical substances.

Diagnostic application

- Biochemical Analysis
- Tools for diagnostic imaging of diseases
- Use of MAB's in RIA & ELISA in the lab are used to measure the circulating concentration of hormones, antigens, interferons, etc
- Cancer
 - To detect certain cancers at early stages by employing mAb's ex I labeled mAb's specific to breast cancer cells when administered to patients detect the spread of cancer – this is not possible by other scanning techniques.
 - To estimate the plasma carcinoembryogenic Ag in colorectal cancer, prostate cancer.
- Pregnancy
- To detect urinary levels of human chorionic gonadotropin
- Hormonal disorders
 - Analysis of thyroxin, triiodothyronine and thyroid stimulating hormones for thyroid disorders.
- Infectious diseases
- To detect circulatory levels of Ag's Specific to infectious agents

MAB's in diagnostic imaging

- Radio labeled MAB's injected intravenously in patients are used in diagnostic imaging of diseases-Immunoscintigraphy
- Radioisotopes commonly used : iodine 131 technetium 99
- Cardiovascular diseases : myocardial infection , deepvein thrombosis

- Myocardial infection: radiolabelled antimyosin mAb's used to detect myosine and site of myocardial infection.
- Deepvein thrombosis : DVT refers to formation of blood clots within blood veins
- MAB's detected against fibrin or platelets can be used

Therapeutic applications

MAB's used to enhance immune system of host with minimal toxicity to target tissues.

1. In destroying disease causing organism
2. In cancer treatment against the surface Ag's of cancer cells
3. In immunosuppression of organ transplantation
4. In treatment of AIDS
5. in treatment of autoimmune disease

Toxins, drugs, radioisotopes can be attached to tissue specific MAB's and carried to target tissues for efficient action

1. MAB's used as immunotoxin (toxins coupled with MAB's).
2. Mab's used in drug delivery
3. MAB's used in isolation of blood clots
4. In radio immune therapy against cancer cells.

Protein purification

- Immobilized MAB's are used for protein purification by immune affinity method.

Advantages

- Binding of highly specific MAB's to desired protein
- Efficient illusion from chromatographic column.
- High degree of purification

Miscellaneous applications

- Catalytic MAB's (abzymes) – antibody enzymes , abzymes are catalytic antibodies used in study of various reactions
- Auto antibody fingerprinting :
 - Individual specific (IS)auto antibodies are produced after birth and reach maximum no .by 2 yrs.
 - MAB's produced against IS –auto Ab's can be used in detection and identification of individuals & criminals.

Side-Effects and Limitations of MABs

MABs given intravenously have usually mild side effects as compared with chemotherapy. A mild allergic reaction (rash) may be occurs with first administration of the drug. Common side effects include fever, headache, weakness, chills, nausea with vomiting and diarrhea, and low blood pressure. Other side effects of MABs are related to the targeted antigens. Bevacizumab (used against tumor blood vessel growth) can have side effects such as kidney damage, high blood pressure, bleeding with poor wound healing, and blood clots. The FDA-approved drug raxibacumab (MAB) injection is used to treat infectious inhalational anthrax when alternative

therapies have failed. Common side effects include rash with itching, extreme pain, and drowsiness.^[30, 31, 32]

CONCLUSION

MAB drugs have always been costly, as only a few of nearly 22 FDA regulated drugs are available in the market. A large number of new MAB drugs are under development. The sale of first-generation safe and cost-effective MABs is quite good in absence of generic competitors. MAB therapies are a financial burden on patients, and with some health plans and step-wise therapies the problem can be resolved. MABs is a proven therapeutic agent generating revenues of several billion dollars for the pharmaceutical industry. The typical doses of MAB drugs needed for treatment are significantly higher than those required for other drugs (or products). Thus, large-scale production that is cost-effective in manufacturing processes are required. However, the huge demand to increase production of these drugs and the drive to lower the cost of these expensive medicines is a continuous challenge to the present industry. This will further improve the efficiency of manufacturing processes. These challenges are overcome by streamlining downstream processes to increase product quantities, to implement proper quality with high-concentration product formulations with sufficient stability, dose-effective products, to reduce the cost, to develop methodologies for timeline MAB production, and to develop alternative delivery systems.

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